

Determinants of Women Empowerment

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Pareesa Fareed Siddiqui ⁽²⁾Ghulam Akbar Mahesar ⁽³⁾Nazia Parveen Gill ⁽⁴⁾Zulfiqar Haider
⁽¹⁾Research Scholar. ⁽²⁾Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, University of Sindh, Pakistan.
⁽³⁾Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, University of Sindh, Pakistan. ⁽⁴⁾Assistant Professor,
Department of Public Administration, University of Sindh, Pakistan.

Correspondence Author: Zulfiqar Haider

Abstract

this paper focused upon understanding the concept of women empowerment and determinants critical to it. The study was conducted in Hyderabad region for determining women empowerment level on five key indicators identified from the literature. Primary data was collected through online questionnaire and informal interviews from randomly selected 200 female and 20 male respondents respectively. Results indicate women empowerment in Hyderabad on four out of five indicators i.e. economic participation, education, health and nutrition and media.

Keywords: Women empowerment, male dominancy, indicators, respondents.

1. Introduction

Empowerment can be defined as taking control of life and making decisions that concerns oneself without others interference. This definition implies that an individual is empowered if he/she has power to make choices and one who doesn't have power to do so is disempowered. Hence it is transition process of an individual from being in a state of powerlessness to becoming powerful.

Women empowerment follows the same definition as it involves shift from powerlessness to powerfulness whereby women go through the process to freely evaluate, develop and express their needs and interests without being influenced by others.

Several measures have been taken at national and international levels to eradicate gender discrimination but all of them have proven to be insufficient in resolving the issue. The most prominent steps taken around the world in this regard include the Society of Defending Women's Rights formed in Saudi Arabia for empowering women and protecting their rights, the Prevention of Immoral Traffic, the Dowry Prevention Act and the Sati Act focusing prevention of widow burning in India, provision of financial assistance to families with girls in both India and China for encouraging female education etc. According to Global Gender Gap Index all countries can perform better in reducing gender gap and globally only North America and Western Europe have less than 30 percent gender gap remaining. Despite number of steps being taken, gender discrimination is still predominant problem around the world irrespective of the country economic status and education attainment.

Pakistan performance in this regard is quite miserable. Majority of the women live in pitiable conditions and their conditions instead of improving are further worsening with the passage of time. This is evident from the World Economic Forum gender biasedness survey that has ranked Pakistan second last on gender equality index for a second consecutive year. This is alarming as Pakistan's performance on gender equality is way behind other South Asian countries. Even war torn Syria performed better than Pakistan with a score of 142. Pakistan is ranked lower than other South Asian countries such as Sri Lanka, Nepal, Maldives and Bhutan which secured 100th, 110th, 115th and 121st spots respectively. Pakistan however, performed better in women Education Attainment with a score of 135, Health and Survival (124) and Political Empowerment (90). The report observed that there were 70 women parliamentarians in the country and 139 on ministerial positions.

Possible factors responsible for such state of affairs are social backwardness, absence of government's interest and involvement in women empowerment and male dominant society. Women in Pakistan do not enjoy all social, educational, political and professional status equal to their male counterparts. This however is much

worse in rural areas because of lack of access to resources, awareness and opportunities. However, power alone does not ensure women empowerment, other factors too have equal role in determining level of women empowerment in the country.

Pakistan is a male-dominant society where men are considered prime authority and women are not allowed to take decisions regarding their health. This has important implication for women physical health. Contrary to Western countries, women in Pakistan are at increased risk of dying due to pregnancy related problems. Almost 50 percent women bearing child suffer from nutritional anemia. Maternal mortality rate in Pakistan is estimated to be between 340 and 600 per hundred thousand live births. This implies that on average one pregnant woman dies in every twenty minutes due to avoidable causes. As of 2012/13 contraceptive prevalence rate was 35.4 percent. Pakistan has one of the highest fertility rates and the lowest contraceptive usage rate resulting in poor reproductive health indicators for women and high neonatal mortality. The male-controlled framework of Pakistani society places women in a weaker position than men as very few women have a say in family planning regardless of the fact that these decisions affect their reproductive health. All this points to the fact that absence of women participation in decision making in this regard critically affect their health and thus their way of life.

Over the years, a large number of laws have been passed to protect women rights in Pakistan. Despite the constitutional and legal guarantees granting women free will, Pakistan is one of the worst countries in terms of ensuring women empowerment and security. Prevailing circumstances of the country show that honor killing is on rise and it claims lives of thousands of women each year. Hardly few cases of such crime are reported due to lack of justice. Honor killing is a bitter reality of our society that needs to be acknowledged. However, action can be taken against the guilty only when such cases are reported. Data suggests 1096 women were killed in the name of honor killing in 2015 whereas in 2013 and 2014 the honor killing claimed lives of 869 and 1005 women respectively. Gender based violence is an important area of concern specially its worst form i.e. domestic violence that includes physical, mental and sexual abuse. In order to address deteriorating conditions of women, Pakistan Parliament has unanimously passed anti-honor killing and anti-rape bills which include strict punishments for people guilty of them. These laws provide 25 years mandatory imprisonment for people found guilty of committing honor killing and rape. Further these laws do not allow victim family right to forgive the guilty.

Pakistan is one of the most populous countries in the world. It has a population of approximately 200 million and its labor force comprises of 57.2 million people out of which 28 percent are women. Though the constitution strictly prohibits discrimination on the basis of race, religion, gender, caste or origin yet it is openly practiced phenomenon particularly against women. Article 26 of 1973 constitution says no person otherwise qualified can be discriminated against in the matter of employment on the basis of race, religion, caste, gender, residence or place of birth (Exceptions: specific services can be reserved for members of either sex if such posts/services require duties which cannot be adequately performed by the members of other sex, e.g. Lady Health Visitor). The constitution specifically provides women equal opportunity to participate in local government, article 32 says special representation shall be given to women in local government institutions (i.e., local bodies). Unfortunately, most women in Pakistan are unaware of their rights regarding employment and are frequently discriminated at work place. The regulatory laws attempt to prevent gender discrimination even then employers are reluctant to hire women due to their divided attention between work and home related responsibilities and long maternity leave. Because of these reasons, World Bank ranks status of Pakistani women among the lowest in the world.

Education is an important tool that could help to empower women by developing self-confidence, skills and knowledge essential to participate in development process. According to article 37 of the Constitution of Pakistan, education is a fundamental right of every individual but gender differences still exist. There are twice males receiving secondary education compare to females (United Nation Development Program, 2011). There are 7.261 million out of school children at primary level and 58 percent of them are females (UNESCO,

Education for All Global Monitoring Report, 2011). Major factors responsible for low female literacy rate are poverty, illiteracy of parents and parental concerns about safety and mobility of their daughters and cultural constraints. Society's emphasis on girl's modesty, protection and early marriages may limit family's willingness to send them to school. Pakistan's public expenditure on education is estimated at 2.2 percent of GDP in fiscal year 2015 compared to 2.1 percent in preceding fiscal year showing an increase of 4.8 percent. These figures show that Pakistan spend less on education compare to other regional countries.

Media has key role to play in empowering women by creating awareness among them about how they could be a force of change in the society. Media in all its forms particularly electronic media has an important role to play in women empowerment and in reducing gender inequality in Pakistan. It can be used as a tool for empowerment by allowing right to freedom of opinion and expression. Given this background, this paper focuses upon finding out the factors determining women empowerment and level of women empowerment in Hyderabad, Pakistan. Particularly, it evaluates the role of economic participation, education attainment, social media, religious values, male dominancy and awareness of legal and constitutional rights in empowering women in the targeted area.

Rest of the paper follows as: in section both theoretical and empirical literature on women empowerment is reviewed. In section detailed discussion on methodology for conducting the study is given followed by key findings in section four. Section 5 concludes the study.

2. Literature Review

Malhotra et al. (2002) reviewed earlier literature on women empowerment and concluded that considerable groundwork has already been done in developing frameworks that specify the dimensions of women empowerment, its relative nature and various levels at which it could be measured. Based on their findings, they recommend procedures for determining indicators for each domain at different levels of aggregation and development of multi-dimensional framework so that women empowerment agenda with more coordinated efforts of data collection could move forward. At aggregate level, a broader range of more sophisticated, gender-disaggregated data is needed. At household level data on important under-utilized indicators such as time use or violence against women need to be frequently collected. Kandpal et al. (2012) studied the impact of Mahila Samakhya program on women empowerment in Uttarkhand district, India. The gathered empirical evidence shows that the program significantly increased access to outside employment compared to women from non-programmed districts. Participants were also more likely to leave the house without the permission of male elder of house. However, participants of both kinds of districts did not participate in village council meeting because it involved their husbands' or in-laws permission. Based on empirical findings, the authors conclude that Mahila Samakhya succeeded in empowering women and recommended its implementation in non-participant villages too. Kumar and Paul (2007) aimed at developing conceptual clarity of term empowerment and other related notions such as gender equality, social inclusion, being powerful etc. and to suggest policy measures to plan empowerment initiatives by women themselves. The research was based on an important indicator of women empowerment i.e. Autonomy in Decision Making on various issues categorized as Trivial Issues, Issues Related to Own Self, Issues Related to Children and Critical Issues among workers and non-workers. The data was gathered through questionnaires. The responses regarding participation in decision-making was found higher for the working women as compared to the non-working women in all aspects of household decision making. All working women had autonomy in issues relating to children. Only 5 percent non-working women were not allowed or did not take part in decision making. However, the participation of working and non-working women in decisions regarding financial matters was constrained. Khan and Moin (2013) focused the contribution of internet in empowering women on several issues including educational opportunities, career advancement facilities, social care system for working women and legal provisions against sexual harassment, domestic violence and social injustice. Based on findings the authors concluded that new media offered women a platform to speak out about their lives, needs and the issues they face. It helped them get knowledge on important issues including health, education and empowerment and share their experiences

which increased their self-confidence, social interaction, sense of achievement and awareness regarding all kinds of subjects. Steffen (2014) evaluated the impact of a community-driven development program known as Rural Development Program (RDP) on women's empowerment in the Solomon Islands. He found increased empowerment of women after the implementation of RDP in targeted area. Based on this finding, the study recommended the implementation of such kind of programs at grass root level for women empowerment and eradication of poverty. Luz and Agadjanian (2015) conducted their research to observe the connection between rural women's decision making autonomy, status of primary school-age children living in their households and how this connection varies with gender of the child. The survey results revealed positive association between women decision making autonomy and enrollment of girl child at primary school. Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that women who had higher levels of decision making autonomy tend to strongly favor for daughter's schooling and had larger say in making decision regarding her education as compared to those women who had lower autonomy levels. Mondal and Chakraborty (2014) examined the role of media in women empowerment among the tribal women of Birbhum district West Bengal. The objectives of the study were to measure the academic achievement of tribal women, to observe their media using habits and to analyze media's role in tribal women empowerment. The survey data shows limited use of media. The interview results revealed media use for entertainment purpose. Based on their empirical findings, the authors recommend provision of education along with access to media for women empowerment in the targeted district. Xiaohui and Ning (2011) examined the influence of male household members on women decision to uptake reproductive health services in Pakistan. The data taken from 2005-2006 Pakistan Social and Living Standards Measurement Survey (PSLM) show low uptake reproductive health services in Pakistan. The results further show positive association of reproductive health services uptake rate and decision-making power with economic status. Women in poor households had less decision-making power than in non-poor households, and relationship between women's decision-making power and household welfare status was found linear. Based on these findings, the authors recommend intervention for empowering women to increase their utilization of health services and targeting influential male household members whose understanding of the importance of maternity services is crucial for increasing effectiveness of health services. Ahmed et al. (2010) examined the relationship between women's economic, educational and empowerment status (3Es) and maternal health service utilization in developing countries. Data was gathered from 31 countries using Demographic and Health Survey. The survey results showed that the poorest 20 percent of women used 74, 84 and 94 percent less of modern contraception, attendance of four or more antenatal care visits and skilled attendance at delivery respectively compare to the richest 20 percent women. Noreen and Khalid (2012) conducted their research for finding out the possibilities and opportunities for women empowerment in Pakistan. Analysis of the data collected from ten women holding senior positions in a woman university show that educated women are more confident and male dominance in household hindered women from acquiring education and making career. Shanmuga and Sakthi (2015) examined the use of social media as a tool for marketing business endeavor by women. The study was conducted in the Chennai city in India. A sample of 50 women with an average age of 18 years who carry out online businesses was selected. The results showed that all the participants used social media to market their products. Based on these findings, the author concludes that social media is helping women to operate online business which empowers them economically. They suggest educating women about rapidly advancing technology for improving their economic status. Ume-Habiba et al. (2016) explored the form of patriarchy operationalized through women at household level and the hidden reality behind patriarchal sustenance. The research was conducted in Rawalpindi district of Pakistan. The data was collected through qualitative method-purposive sampling with a total of seventeen cases and two focus group discussions. The results show that patriarchy is promoted and supported primarily by women. The native women (mothers and sisters in law) strengthen patriarchy by exploiting the new women (new brides) to maintain their power in the family. Both case studies and focus group discussion results reveal mother's training to their daughters to be submissive and obedient from early age, internalization of patriarchy by mother in law and men's desire to maintain their power are the factors behind the sustenance of patriarchy in the society. Based on the results, authors recommend the parents specifically mothers to stop teaching their daughters to be fragile and inferior to their male counterparts.

3. Methodology

The study is conducted using both qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative method included Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). There were six key interviews taken from twenty male respondents. The quantitative method included collecting data through online survey questionnaire with closed-ended multiple choice and likert scale questions from 200 female participants. Both male and female respondents were randomly selected. Out of 200 female respondents; 92 were single, 91 were married; 8 and 9 were divorced and widowed respectively. The sample included educated/uneducated and employed/unemployed women aged 18-55 years. The online questionnaire was designed to estimate level of empowerment among women of Hyderabad through questions that analyze where they stand based on the indicators identified i.e. economic/work participation, legal rights awareness and practices, health and nutrition, education and media.

The male participants aged between 20-60 years out of which three have completed matriculation and were employed with a salary of 25,000-30,000, five were pursuing a bachelor's degree in different fields, five have graduated and were employed, two were pursuing a master's degree and were employed too and the remaining five were post graduates having salaries of more than 80,000. The data was collected from them through structured interviews to answer three open ended questions i.e. how the participants perceive women empowerment, do they support their mothers, wives and sisters empowerment and how do they see the future of women empowerment in Pakistan.

4. Key Findings

Results reveal that majority of the respondents have say in home chores and financial matters. Survey results show that majority of the respondents have say in cooking, monthly expenditures and saving, family planning, purchasing requirements and children education, income spending, expenditures on family wedding, purchase of property, political affiliation, planning of vacations, health care and hanging out with friends and colleagues. 49.5 percent respondents themselves selected the field of education and institution; both parents took decision of education field and institutions for 29.5 percent respondents' male head for 19 percent and guardian for 2 percent respondents.

The female respondents were given different statements to comment upon. Results show that 63 percent of respondents agreed that they are as intelligent as men, 57 percent respondents agreed that working women are valued more compare to non-working women, 62.5 percent respondents agreed that man and women should be paid equally for the same job, 48 percent agreed that some jobs suit man and some to woman, 48 percent disagreed with the statement that man should have a job and woman should stay at home and take care of family and children, 61.5 percent disagreed that man should take decision and women should obey them, only 46 percent respondents were aware of the rights the constitution provides them, 62 percent knew their religious rights and 48.5 percent agreed that internet has helped them enhance their knowledge and voice their opinion. As far as permission to study in co-education is concerned, 74.9 percent agreed that they were permitted to study in co-education system. 62.4 percent respondents told that they are not the part of any community (local, national or international). 189 respondents responded to the question whether they went through terms/conditions/women rights given in Nikahnama apart from Haq-Mehr section. Only 32.8 percent respondents told that they read the terms and conditions of Nikahnama while 39.2 did not. Rest of the respondents was unmarried. Furthermore, 66.1 percent respondents intended to go through the terms or conditions given to them in their Nikahnama when they would get married while 33.9 percent responded that they won't. 98 percent of the respondents never reported any crime or harassment while 2 percent did.

The results obtained from key informant interviews reveal that 71.5 percent of the participants perceived women empowerment positively and emphasized its practice on a greater level in terms of education, economic participation and legal rights. The aged participants who were educated believed in women empowerment yet they emphasized that empowerment should not be equated with equality to men. The remaining three participants who were less educated were not aware of the concept of women empowerment but when told

about it, they expressed that they do not see it as an important concern apart from education and that too for financial assistance.

The young participants of the study who were unmarried told that they supported their female relatives' empowerment by encouraging their mothers to participate in families' financial matters and supported their sisters to go for higher education and pursue the profession of their choice.

The middle aged married males favored empowerment of their wives and sisters, their pursuit of further education and hanging-out with their friends. They also favored their mothers' equal participation in household issues. However, they strictly opposed females' legal empowerment or joining local or national government or any party.

The aged participants affirmed their females' empowerment on certain matters such as household decision making, health related issues, family planning decisions (for wives) and education. Further discussion with them revealed that they supported their daughters' education for maintaining their standard in the society, for finding out good spouse for them when they grow up and not with an intention to empower them. Also, they were not in favor of their wives, daughters and daughter in laws doing a job until and unless their male counterparts needed financial assistance. This thought reveals our cultural, religious and societal norms that put financial responsibility of family on males and expect females to perform household chores

The remaining three participants who were less educated expressed that they let their wives and daughters to be empowered in household decision making and in matters related to their health to some extent. They agreed that education is important but it is not their prime concern for their children. They educated their children if it is affordable and preferred to educate their sons first as they could be the bread-earners for the family in future whereas spending money on their daughters' education would be of no benefit for them in long run as they will get married and take care of their new family and home.

As far as awareness about women empowerment is concerned, the young participants told that awareness about women empowerment like rest of the world is gradually spreading in Pakistan as well and very soon women empowerment in Pakistan would also become an important area of concern. They all agreed that females today are lot more powerful than they were in the past. They have realized their worth and their true potential to not only make their own choices but also to contribute in growth and development of Pakistan.

The middle aged participants do not see advancement in women empowerment in Pakistan, at least not in near future and that progress in this matter can be achieved only when overall education and awareness is spread.

The responses from aged respondents who are less educated reveal that women empowerment is relatively a new concept in Pakistan specifically for their social class and for the classes below them whose central focus is adequate food, clothing and security. They believe that women empowerment may be achieved at superficial level but they do not see bright future for women in the entire country because majority of the people belong to their social class.

All participants however agreed that no matter to what extent this issue is discussed, there are certain religious, cultural and societal constraints that limit women to look after the family and children and men to shoulder financial responsibility of the family. Such kind of constraints hinder women empowerment at different levels.

5. Conclusion

This paper focused on identifying the factors that qualify a woman for being empowered and level of empowerment among women of Hyderabad, Pakistan. The existing literature indicates economic participation, health and nutrition, education, legal rights and media as the most important determinants of women empowerment. This implies that women are empowered if they have freedom of choice and equality to men along these dimensions.

The results obtained from the survey data show that economic participation and attainment of education have positive association with women empowerment in the targeted area. Media particularly social media has key role in creating awareness among the women about their legal and constitutional rights that empowers them. Religious values and male dominancy do not hinder women empowerment and awareness of legal and constitutional rights do not in any way imply women empowerment. The responses collected from female participants through survey questionnaire indicates that women are empowered along four of the five identified indicators i.e. economic participation, education, health and nutrition and media while they are not empowered legally.

The feedback from male respondents through informal interviews indicates that aged participants neither consider women empowerment an issue nor they see bright future for women empowerment in Pakistan. The younger participants however, support their women to be empowered and consider it a positive aspect that should be practiced on a greater level for positive contribution of women in economic growth and development of the country. Since youth is supportive of women empowerment so we can conclude that women empowerment will gradually gain acceptance in the society and they will eventually know their worth and true potential to excel in all aspects of life.

References

Ahmed, S., Creanga, A.a., Gillespie, D.G., and Tsui, A.O., (2010) Economic status, education and empowerment: implications for maternal health service utilization in developing countries. *PLoS ONE*, Vol. 5(6), pp. 1-6.

Kandpal, E., Baylis, K., and Arends-Kenning, M., (2012) Empowering women through education and influence: An evaluation of the Indian Mahila Samakhya Program. *IZA Discussion Paper No. 6347*. Bonn Germany.

Khan, E.A., and Moin, A., (2013) Women empowerment: role of new media. *Excellence International Journal of Education and Research*, Vol. 1(3), pp. 206-216.

Kumar and Paul (2007) Empowerment of Women, concept, policy approach and implications, paper presented in a Seminar on *Gender Issues and Empowerment of Women*, Indian statistical Institute, Kolkata.

Luz, L. and Agadjanian, V., (2015) Women's decision making autonomy and children's schooling in rural Mozambique. *Demographic Research*, Vol. 32, pp. 775-796.

Malhotra, A., Schuler, S.R., and Boender, C. (2002) Measuring women's empowerment as a variable in international development. Background paper prepared for the World Bank workshop on poverty and gender: new perspectives

Mondal, D. and Chakraborty, D. (2014) Women empowerment through media: an empirical study on the development of tribals of rural Bengal. *New Man International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, Vol. 1(3), pp. 305-314.

Noreen, G. and Khalid, H. (2012) Gender Empowerment through women's higher education: opportunities and possibilities. *Journal of Research and Reflections in Education*, Vol.6(1), pp 50-60.

Shanmuga and Sakthi (2015) Social media a tool for economic empowerment of women. *International Journal of Applied Research*, Vol. 1(5), pp 157-160.

Steffen, E.M., (2014) Women's Empowerment and Community-Driven Development: Evidence from the Solomon Islands. Master's Thesis No. 90, Department of Economics, University of San Francisco.

Ume-Habiba, Ali, R., and Ashfaq, A., (2016) From patriarchy to neopatriarchy: experiences of women from

Pakistan, *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, Vol. 6 (3), pp. 212-221.

United Nations Development Program (2011) Human Development Report.

United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (2011) Education for all: Global Monitoring Report.

Xiahui, H., and Ning, M., (2011) Empowering women: the effect of women's decision making power on reproductive health services uptake, evidence from Pakistan. Policy Research Working Paper No. WPS 5543, Washington DC. World Bank.